

On the Microwave Assisted Extraction of High Added Value Compounds from Spent Coffee Grounds

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ABSTRACT

Spent coffee grounds (SCGs) are one of the most promising biomasses, created in huge volumes every year. SCGs rich chemistry makes it an excellent feedstock for an integrated smart biorefinery, targeting the realization of the “cradle to cradle” circular economy concept. The antioxidant activity in SCGs is chiefly ascribed to polyphenols, and among the available techniques, microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) is considered to be one of the most favorable for their green and mild extraction. In our study we used a microwave apparatus CEM model SP Discover.

Design of experiments (DOE) is an important tool for optimization, which scrutinizes the performance of a process in order to understand how it is affected by the variation of operating parameters. Thus, to find the factors of the greatest importance in an experiment, two level factorial designs can be the choice whereas to optimize the previously found influential factors within a predetermined range, more complex designs like Central Composite Design (CCD) are appropriate.

In our study, DOE was applied in a fractional factorial design for 4 factors, namely power (60-120 W), solvent/material ratio (5-20 mL/g), solvent composition (50-99 %, ethanol/water) and time (3-6 min) and for 2 responses (yield of extraction and total content of polyphenols in the extracts). Maximum temperature of 70 °C was set to control any possible degradation of polyphenols during extraction. Screening analysis showed higher significance of solvent/material ratio and solvent composition. Then, CCD was used to optimize the process. The factors in this case were solvent/material ratio (10-20 mL/g), solvent composition (50-70 %, ethanol/water), while the yield of extraction and total content of polyphenols were the response. Power and time were maintained at 90 W and 4.5 min, respectively. As a result of the CCD analyses the central point determined with regard to the extraction yield and the maximum of polyphenols content is 6.61 % and 0.167 mgGAE/mg, respectively. In a follow up procedure, these results will be compared with the CCD predicted equations to demonstrate the importance of process parameters optimization and their influence on the yield of dry extract and phenolic compounds content. To the best of our knowledge no previous studies on MAE of SCGs have been reported in the literature till present applying the above described methodology.

Keywords: spent coffee grounds, phenolic compounds; microwave-assisted extraction; DOE, RMS

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